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JOHN S. MILL'S CRITIQUE OF MAJORITARIAN DEMOCRACY: AN EVALUATION

ABSTRACT

Democracy, based on its qualities—freedom and equality, etc., and its operational basis of majority consent, calls for critical evaluation. The problem associated with the “tyranny of the majority” is devastating and requires proper critical analysis. John S. Mill argued extensively that democracy by majority rule/consent is purely a denial of the freedom of individuals to participate actively in the government of the people. In furtherance, he emphasized that the idea of “the majority” in a democratic system of government is absolutely the minority ruling class, exclusively represented. By implication, it means democracy could be taken to be synonymous with an oligarchy system of governance. For many who advocate that democracy is the system of governance that operates on a majoritarian modus operandi, call for proper modification of the system. Moreover, Mill was of the view that democracy can comfortably and pragmatically work on its solid idea of the ideal principle of equal representation and affirmed the idea of equal democracy. Therefore, the paper evaluates his recommendation of equal democracy as being minimalistic in nature against the encompassing nature of democracy. Although every system, knowledge, or idea stands to be falsified but the implications of his recommended type of democracy (equal democracy) are enormous and devastating. Then there is a need for wide representation (the poor and the rich) in the democratic system of governance for its majoritarian modus operandi to be sustained. It would also be protected by its tenets or qualities—freedom and equality, etc.

Keywords: Democracy, Freedom, Equality, Majority, Election.

INTRODUCTION

John S. Mill, a philosopher and economist, projected the idea that “the people” by whom democracy is known are not the people in general, but the few in the legislative chambers are regarded as the majority, which mainly constitute or are recognized as the minority of the whole, exclusively represented. His interest was in assisting democracy to reaffirm its mandate and fulfill its qualities, precisely the equality of all. The cardinal promise of democracy, for him, centred on equality to all, and for that to be realistic, he advocated for a type of democracy – equal democracy. The essence is to get our democracy rid of a despotic and oligarchic system. J. S. Mill’s critique of democracy on its modus operandi was informed by the unjust neglect of the minority by the people in the corridors of power (Executive, Legislative, and Judiciary). He was interested in how power could be returned to “people”, not to “few”. The ideas of equal representation and freedom were his major interests. He kicked against the so-called “tyranny of the majority” that does not involve the people holistically.

The rulers were taken to be antagonistic to the people who voted them into some political positions. They projected the system of governance that was exclusively for the few, which was associated with the governing of one tribe or caste, against the yearnings of the governed. The essence of his idea of equal representation and liberty was for inclusive participation and representation of the masses, and to set a limit on the power of the rulers over the community and the people. This limitation is what he called freedom or liberty. This was carried out in two major ways; first, obtaining certain immunities called political liberties or rights, then it would be regarded as a breach of duty in the ruler to infringe, and if it infringed, certain resistance or general rebellion would take place, and such remain justifiable. The second is the constitutional checks, which are expedient and remain important acts for governing power. There, the interests of the masses, communities, and bodies are represented. The major target is to limit the liberty or the freedom of the rulers and the governed. The governing power and the people subject themselves to the constitutional checks. The idea of democracy being the power of the people over themselves remains submerged in practice. The will of the people is regarded as the will of the numerous or the most active part of the people; the majority or those who succeeded in making themselves accepted as the majority. The people (majority) may desire to be tyrannical to a certain part of their number (few). Therefore, resistance or precautions are most needed against this, as against the abuse of power (tyranny of the majority). The limitation of the power of government over individuals

remains relevant and paramount, most especially when the people are regularly and constantly accountable to the community (poor and rich people).

The tyranny of the majority operates through the acts of the public authorities. When there is social tyranny, it would be difficult to restrict the ones that develop through the attitude or hands of the political functionaries. The society is itself a tyrannical society that collectively over some separate individuals who are members of such society. Likewise, society can execute its mandate through wrong – right ways. If invariably in the wrong way, it becomes social tyranny, and such is more formidable than many kinds of political oppression. As it is important to protect against the tyranny of the people in power, likewise, it is also very necessary to protect against the tyranny of the prevailing opinion and feeling. Mainly, to prevent the unwarranted conditions or circumstances of society from being imposed by other means than civil penalties. There is a proper limitation to the legitimate interference of collective opinions with an individual's ways of life. To maintain and safeguard human affairs, it remains necessary to find the limit and maintain it against any encroachment. Maintaining human affairs centred on the good aspect would offer protection against political despotism. The fundamental and practical questions are where to place the limit and how to make the required adjustments between an individual's independence and social control. Existence remains important to everyone based on the enforcement of restraints on the actions of other people. Although some rules of conduct should be in place to checkmate the activities of men but what these rules should be is the subject of analysis. Those rules should be in place to grant liberty to individuals, and whatever actions exhibited by the individuals should not directly or indirectly harm others. Then, with the idea of individual eccentricity and the right to be different, such would automatically reduce and make the issue of "tyranny of the majority" invisible. The unjust neglect of the minority, particularly the poor masses, by the ruling class in the guise of democracy would not lead to the development of the state and the individuals. The state solely must protect the liberty of its subjects. Liberty remains a necessary condition for developing one's deepest potential. In handling the issues raised in this essay, the following would be considered: Democracy, John S. Mill's Critique of Majoritarian Democracy, Analysis of Political Freedom, Evaluation, and Conclusion

DEMOCRACY

Democracy originated from the Greek word “demos” and “cracy” which means “the people” and “rule” respectively. It means the rule of the people.¹ Then Nweke in his book, *Fundamentals of Political Ideology* was of the same view that democracy has its origin from the two Greek words which means “rule by the people”². The question that remains fundamental to us in this essay is; who are the people? The majority that are tyrannical for J. S. Mill or the few that are recognized as the minority in political practice. According to Heywood³ ‘the people’ could be referred as the poor and disadvantaged. Therefore, he emphasized that democracy has to do with “a system of rule by the poor and disadvantaged. Furthermore, a form of government by which direct and continuous rule by the people is obtainable devoid of professional politicians or public officials; a society strongly established through equal opportunity and individual merit as against hierarchy and privilege etc.

Considering the position of the Greeks on democracy, the legacy of Athens can be **obtained** and gotten through the works of famous Greek thinkers: Plato, Aristotle, Xenophon, Thucydides, and Herodotus. Plato in his book “The Republic” says that democracy originates when the poor win, kill or exile their opponents and give the rest equal civil rights and opportunities of office, appointment to office, being, as a rule, by lot. In furtherance, Mbachu gave the characteristics of Plato’s idea of democracy, **which** involves the liberty and freedom of speech in plenty, and every individual is free to do what he likes.⁴ In his analysis, he emphasized that Plato was for a philosopher king to be a ruler, in handling the responsibility of government. The reason is that the masses are ignorant, lack the wisdom and experience to rule. Aristotle, like Plato, was against democracy but had **great** interest in the consent of the people (the ruled) above any other thing in his book *The Politics*. If a man of virtue (one who moderates his actions) becomes a monarch, for Aristotle, “all should joyfully obey such a ruler, according to what seems to be the order of nature”. He prefers monarchy because ‘king is the resources of the better classes against the project’ then “the idea of a king is to be a protector of the rich against unjust treatment and of the people against insult and oppression”⁵. For Aristotle, the fundamental basis of democracy is liberty that, “one principle of liberty is for all to rule and be ruled in turn ...that whatever the majority approve must be the end and the just. Every citizen, it is said, must have equality”.

Democracy for J.S. Mill involves the consent of all (poor and rich) minorities and the majority. The theories of some philosophers in the medieval period provided a better ground for the defence of democracy. Then in the Middle Ages, some theories came into existence which include theories of individual rights, political and judicial; theories concerning limited executive power, theories of representative government, including the theories of constitutional government. In more clarification, Cicero was of the view that the true law was in existence, namely right reason that was in accordance with nature, which is applied to all men and remains unchangeable and eternal. Those laws serve as a command for men to carry out their duties and restrict them from doing wrong. Furthermore, in the modern period, the notion of democracy had its foundation in the medieval concept of law. John Locke, in the modern period, precisely in his book, *An Essay Concerning the True Origin, Extent and End of Civil Government*, considered democracy as:

The majority having as has been showed, upon men's first uniting into society, the whole power of the community naturally in them, employ all that power in making laws for the community from time to time and executing those laws by officials of their own appointing and then the form of the government is a perfect democracy; or else may put the power of making laws into the hands of few selected men, and their heirs or successors, and then it is a monarchy; if to him and his heirs, it is a hereditary monarchy; if to him only for life but upon his death the power only of nominating a successor, to return to them, an elective monarchy.

Locke's notion of democracy was informed by his political theory on man, when he emphasized that, "state of nature has a law to him, which obliges everyone and reason which is that law, teaches all mankind who will but consult it, that being all equal and independent, no one ought to harm another in his life, health, liberty or possessions". On the [other hand](#), Hobbes, on the idea of man's rationality, was of the view that life in the state of nature is solitary, poor, nasty, brutish, and short. That man is selfish; he is moved to action not by his reasoning (rationality) or intellect but by his desire, passion, and appetites, which means that law and justice are not obtainable in the state of nature.⁹ Therefore, democracy remains the best system of governance because it is for all, that was why J.S. Mill stated that democracy is a government by the consent of all.

John S. Mill's Critique of Majoritarian Democracy

Many advocated that democracy is a government by the majority's consent, and many opponents like J.S. Mill criticized it on this majoritarian inclination. J.S. Mill, in his book *On Liberty and Other Essays*, understood democracy as:

The government of the whole people is by a mere majority of the people exclusively represented. The latter, strongly confounded with it, is a government of privileged, in favour of the numerical majority who alone possess practically any voice in the state. This is the inevitable consequence of the manner in which the votes are now taken to the complete disenfranchisement of minorities.

For J. S. Mill, this is known as the “tyranny of the majority” over the few called the minority. It was not on the lawlessness or physical oppression of the poor (weak) by the despots. It is important and necessary to note that he was against the modus operandi of democracy that is based on representation. The modern democracy is purely characterized by representation. “In a representative body actually deliberating” and “the minority must of course be overruled; and in an equal democracy (since the opinions of the constituents, when they insist on them, determine those of the representative body) the majority of the people through their representatives will in number outvote and prevail over the minority and their representatives. Then, on the side of the minority, does it follow that the minority should have no representatives at all? On the ground that the majority ought to prevail over the minority, must the majority have all the votes, and the minority none? Is it required and necessary that the minority should not even be heard?”

J. S. Mill identified explicitly the philosophies of Hobbes and Plato as against democracy. He was of the view that the choice of the majority could be likely determined by the portion of the body that are most timid, the most narrow minded and prejudiced or who cling most tenaciously to the exclusive class interest; in which case the electoral rights of the minority while useless for the purpose of which votes are given, serve only for compelling majority to accept the candidate of the weakest or worst portion for themselves¹². Therefore, many democratic nations based on Mills' position, whose candidates mostly presidential or gubernatorial elections, have no representatives in the upper and lower chambers. The minority parties that could not win the election have no representatives in the legislative bodies at all. Then by implication, the minority

parties or individual persons, as the case may be, have no part in decision-making concerning the issues that affect a nation. In elaborate form, J.S. Mill emphasized that:

It is not only the minority who suffer. Democracy, thus constituted, does not even attain its ostensible object, that of giving the powers of government in all cases of the numerical majority. It does something very different..... it gives them to a majority of the majority, who maybe and often are, but a majority of the wholesuppose then, that in a country governed by equal and universal suffrage, there is a contested election in every constituency and every election is carried by a small majority. The parliamentary thus brought together represents little more than of bare majority of the people. This parliament proceeds to legislate and adopts important measures by a bare majority of itself. What guarantee is there that these measures accord with the wishes of a majority of the people? Nearly half the electors, having been outvoted at the hustings, have had no influence at all in the decision; and the whole of these, may be a majority of them probably are hostile to the measures, having voted against those by whom they have been carried. Of the remaining electors, nearly half have chosen representatives who, by supposition have voted against the measures. It is possible, therefore, and not at all improbable, that the opinion which has prevailed was agreeable only to a minority of the nation, through a majority of that portion of it, whom the institutions of the country have erected into a ruling class.

Based on the *modus operandi* of democracy J. S. Mill reduced it to a government of a minority while majority in disguise. Emphatically, the minority is the people whose freedom can be trampled upon by the leaders in order to succeed. According to Patrick Henry at the second Virginia convention in 1775, he stated, "I know not what course others may take, but as for me, give me liberty or give me death."¹⁴ This explains the essence of people **having** political freedom. Likewise, John Stuart Mill was of the view that "the only purpose for which power can be rightfully exercised over any member of a civilized

community, against his will, is to prevent harm to others”¹⁵. Therefore, for him on his utilitarian moral theory, which has a great impact on his idea of political freedom, advocates that every rational person, particularly the adult in a civilized society, should be given the required liberty to do whatever he or she wishes or wants. On the condition that the person is not harming other people in a way that violates their rights. The only justification for the state's interference in one's life is solely to protect people from irrational and unjustified harm. It means that for democracy to be in its objective nature, the rights of everybody should be protected for the proper participation of all. A situation where the minority becomes the majority, thereby becoming tyrannical in nature (tyranny of the majority), would be a problem. The rights of all would be violated, making the state a state of warfare.

Mill actually has his idea of human freedom rooted in his theory of human nature. Human beings are, by nature, progressive beings that need to be free to develop their highest potential. These potentials precisely require a moral community and personal moral development with deep moral excellence. Then the period to inculcate character is childhood but at the adulthood tolerance should rule both in offensive and destructive behaviours of individuals. Mill was interested in the political freedom where liberty is simply the absence of external coercion on a person. It is the freedom to do whatever we want without being interfered with by others. In the eyes of Isaiah Berlin, It is negative liberty. For the political freedom to be actualized through the deep sense of moral excellence there should be positive liberty. For Isaiah Berlin positive liberty “has to do with the genuine freedom to become your real or rational self”. Mill actually emphasized that democracy remain superior to other forms of government because the rights and interest of every person are being secured from being disregarded only when the person interested is himself able and habitually disposed to stand up for them. He argued out rightly that democracy was the safest form of government.

ANALYSIS OF POLITICAL FREEDOM

Here, man is free to the degree to which nobody interferes with his activities. The political freedom in this angle is simply the time when a man can act undisturbed or unobstructed by others. Man is free in this sense when he carries out his activities without hindrance from anybody. The wider the area of non-interference, the wider one's freedom. So this is what the classical political philosophers understood when they used this word. Their disagreement centred on how wide the area could or should be. For them, it should not be unlimited.

If it were in the state, men could boundlessly interfere with all other men. Automatically, it would lead to a state of warfare, thereby creating social chaos in which men's minimum needs would not be satisfied, or else the liberty of the weak would be suppressed by the state. Those political philosophers perceived that human purposes and activities do not automatically be in harmony with one another. Therefore, because of that, they put high pre-eminence, high value towards the following: justice or happiness, culture or security, or varying degrees of equality. They were very interested in curtailing freedom in the interests of other values and indeed of freedom itself. Then, without this, it would be impossible to have or create the kind of association or group of people that are of a high standard and desirable.

Consequently, it is taken by all these political philosophy thinkers that the area of men's freedom or liberty (men's actions) must not be unlimited. For them, it must be limited by law. In support of that, there are some political philosophers (Locke and Mill in England, and Constant and Tocqueville in France) who were of the view that there ought to exist a certain minimum area of personal freedom which must not be violated. Then for if it is overstepped, the people or as an individual will find himself in a narrow angle, for even that minimum development of his natural faculties which alone makes it possible to pursue and even to conceive, the various ends which men hold good or right or sacred. It means that in drawing the frontier, it must be between the area of private life and that of public authority. Where to be drawn is a matter of argument, indeed of haggling. Men as independent as they are, their activities are not sole completely private to obstruct the lives of others. Freedom for the pike is death, for the minnows, the liberty of some must depend on the restraint of others. Therefore "freedom for an Oxford don" others have been known to add, "is a very different thing from freedom for an Egyptian peasant" it remains true that the freedom of some must at times be curtailed to secure the liberty of other people. The question now is in what principle this should be done? Mill with his much interest in human nature believes that social harmony and progress where compatible with referring a large area for private life by which the state and any other authority must not be allowed to trespass. Hobbes and other conservative and reactionary thinkers argued that if men were to be prevented from destroying one another, solid and greater safeguards must be put in their places. They advocated for the area of centralized control and a decrease that of the individual.

Some portion of human existence must remain or be taken to be independent of the sphere of social control, according to them. Despotism would arise if one invades the areas that are preserved. Benjamin Constant, the defender of freedom and privacy, declared that at the very least, the liberty of religion, opinion, and expression, and property must be guaranteed, devoid of arbitrary invasion. Jefferson, Burke, Paine, and Mill compiled different catalogues concerning individual liberties. Concerning the area of keeping the authority out bay is always the same. We must preserve a minimum area of personal freedom if we are not embarrassed, and belittled, or denied our nature. We cannot be absolutely free; some of our liberty must be given up in order to safeguard and preserve the rest. The idea of total surrender is self-defeating. What is actually the minimum? It involves that which a man cannot give up without offending against the essence of his human nature. Then, what is this essence, and what are the standards that it entails? That area remains a place of constant debate. Regarding the principle, in terms of which area of non-interference is to be drawn, whether it is that of natural law or natural rights or of utility or the pronouncements of a categorical imperative or the sanctity of the social contract or any other concept with which men have sought to make justifications and clarification of their convictions. Liberty in this angle means liberty from which involves the absence of interference beyond shifting but always recognizable, frontier.

The only freedom which deserves the name is that of pursuing our own good in our own pattern; if this is obtainable, is compulsion ever justified? Mill did not doubt this, since justice demands that all individuals be entitled to a certain minimum of freedom, while other individuals may necessary to be restrained, if need be, through force from depriving anyone of it. So, the function of the law is to prevent collisions. The state becomes a night watchman or traffic policeman concerning our actions. The sacredness of Mill's position concerning the protection of individual liberty lies in his famous essay, by which he declares that unless men are allowed to live as they want, precisely in the path which merely concerns themselves, civilization cannot be actualized or advanced. The fact is that it is not only the problem of a lack of a free market in ideas, but there would be no scope or avenue of originality, spontaneity, genius for mental energy, and for moral courage. The implication is that the society would be destroyed by the weight of "collective mediocrity"; the custom would crush whatever that is rich and diversified via men's constant tendency to conformity, which paves the way for only "withered capacities", "pinched and hidebound" "cramped and warped" human beings.

The defence of liberty consists in the “negative” goal of warding off interference. How can we have a good system of democratic governance where individual freedom and liberty are caged and trampled upon? A situation where the society is crushed by collective mediocrity. Mill advocated for critical, original, imaginative, independent, non-conforming to the point of eccentricity, and so on. For him, the truth can be found, and such character can only develop in the conditions of freedom. Democracy can only be the best, as he (Mill) stated, when it is for all, precisely in line with the conditions of freedom and liberty. Mill argued that the best form of democracy is equal democracy. For him, it is the only true form of democracy. The idea is achievable practically representative government. He stated that equal democracy is:

The pure idea of democracy, according to its definition, is the government of the whole people equally represented. Democracy as commonly conceived and hitherto practiced is the government of the whole people by a mere majority of the people exclusively represented. The former is synonymous with the equality of all citizens; the latter is strongly confounded with it, is a government of privileged, in favour of the numerical majority, who alone possess practically any voice in the state.¹⁹

For Mill to enthrone equal democracy and eradicate majoritarian democracy, the alternative remains Mr. Thomas Hare’s reform Bill, enshrined in his book titled *Treatise on the Election of Representatives*. Mr. Hare’s proposal is that; the unity of representation, the quota of electors who would be entitled to have a member to themselves would be known by the ordinary process of taking averages, the number of voters being divided by the number of seats in the house: and every candidate who obtained or reached that quota would be returned from however great a number of local constituencies it might be gathered. The votes would, as at present, be given locally, but any elector would be at liberty to vote for any candidate in whatever part of the country he might offer himself. Those electors, therefore, who did not wish to be represented by any of the local candidates might aid by their vote in the return of a person they like best among all those throughout the country, who expressed a willingness to be chosen. This would so far give reality to the electoral right of the otherwise virtually disenfranchised minority. But it is important that not only those alone who refuse to vote for any of the local candidates, but those who exercised their franchise in voting and are defeated, should be enabled or given the opportunity to find

elsewhere the representation which they have not succeeded in obtaining in their own district. Therefore, it is provided that an elector may deliver a voting paper that has other names in addendum to the one which stands foremost in his preference or choice. His vote would only be counted for one candidate; if the object of his first choice failed to be returned due to lack of obtaining the quota, his second becomes the alternative which might be more fortunate. His list may be extended to a greater number based his order of preference or choice, so that if the names which are very close to the top of the list either cannot meet up to the quota or are able to make it up without his vote, the vote may still be valuable for someone whom it may help in returning. In obtaining the required number of members to complete the house, and also to prevent very popular or famous candidates from engrossing nearly all the suffrages, it is important and necessary that many vote candidate has or have obtained, that no more of them than the quota should be counted for their return. Then the remainder of those who voted for him would have their votes counted for the next person on their respective lists who needed them, which would assist to complete the quota.

Consequently, to determine or ascertain which of the candidate's vote should be used for his return which set free for other several or different methods have been proposed. He would mainly retain the votes of all those who would not otherwise be represented, and concerning the remainder, drawing lots in default of better would be an unobjectionable expedient. For the votes to be counted, the voting papers would be taken to the central office where the votes would be counted, the number of first, second, third and other votes given for each candidate would be ascertained and the quota would be allotted to everyone who could make it up, until the number of the house was complete; first votes being preferred to second, second to third and so forth. The voting papers and all the elements of calculations would be kept in public repositories, accessible to all whom they concerned, and if anyone who had obtained the quota was not returned, it would be in his power easily to prove it.²⁰ Hare's proposal remains necessary for the improvement of democracy, which substantiates the idea of equal democracy recommended by Mill, but there are a lot of pitfalls that need to be addressed in the duo ideas. The following areas need more analysis and clarification: equality and liberty, representative government. Hare's reform Bill vis-à-vis Mill's definition of equal democracy, the condition of Mills' recommendation in representative democracy.

EVALUATION AND CONCLUSION

Mill presents a position that would enhance democracy and reduce the problems that are associated with human nature. It would be more rational if J. S. Mill took equality and liberty as part of democracy that needs proper enhancement for its majoritarian nature to be developed. The essence is to reduce the idea of seeing the majority as a mere majority in the legislature, and secondly, in abolishing the idea of taking the minority as that which is obtainable in a given nation. Defining democracy in terms of equality and liberty is not a solution to the problem; rather, the majority principle of democracy remains the fulcrum by which it is anchored. The problem of human nature regarding democracy in that area needs to be tackled to improve the principles of democracy, especially in the areas of equality and liberty. The overt and covert meaning of majoritarian democracy can only be developed when the intrinsic nature of its principles is protected and enhanced. It remains wrong when a particular principle is used to define a concept (democracy) that has many principles, thereby reducing the essential meaning, which involves the issues that affect all must be decided by all. This important feature differentiates it from other forms of government: aristocracy, oligarchy, and monarchy etc. Equally, considering those who feel that democracy is not desirable and cannot be achieved. Onah, in his article *Africa and the Illusion of Democracy* argued that democracy is neither possible, necessary, nor even desirable. What Abraham Lincoln considered as “Government of the people by the people and for the people” was considered by Onah as “Government of the people, by the parties, for the powerful or as exploitation of the people, by the powerful through the parties”. Actually, Onah’s reasons were that, “Political parties are hijacked by the rich and powerful, the representatives mostly are not elected by the people, and most decisions are made outside legislative houses, and the legislature at best serves as a rubber stamp.”²¹ Onah’s position does not stand because the problem concerning democracy is the problem of human nature. A democratic system of government is desirable and possible when we address the egocentric part of man.

As Mill advocates for representative government as the best option for the form of government, the questions are: can the choice of the representatives be actualized or made visible and known, devoid of elections or lots? As different as human beings are in perception and understanding, is it possible to have unanimous agreement to make a choice or cast their lots for selected candidates in an election process? In making laws and decisions when involving the interests of both the minority and majority in a particular democracy, is proportional representation obtainable or realistic? Furthermore, considering Hare's Reform

Bill and Mill's idea of equal democracy, is Hare's Reform Bill an absolute replica of Mill's concept of equal democracy? Finally, considering the nature of representative democracy, is J.S. Mill's opinion or recommendation a viable option and practicable in a representative democracy? Mr. Hare's recommendation is a complicated matter. He suggests that to ensure that every elector is represented in the House, he should be given chances to have many candidates to vote for to complete his quota, thereby having the chance to represent the minority voters. It is complicated and remains impartial than a democracy that has a majoritarian system as the *modus operandi* which a voter is entitled to one vote in order to elect a candidate. Although if Hare's recommendation is practicable, it can offer a great opportunity to not losing at all. It would solve the problem of voters not losing the right to be represented by a candidate of their own choice. It would destroy and rule out rightly what Mill refers to as disenfranchisement of the minorities in a democracy.

Then, taking Mill's definition of democracy to be Hare's Reform Bill recommendation, by which one man one vote system and one man many votes system remain an overly complicated matter that calls for critical analysis. If it is so, what is Mill's defence of equal democracy? The end of Mill's analysis of Mr. Hare's electoral scheme is **contradictory**. If using lots should be the possible option to choose the candidate who should be given the remaining votes, it then follows that the issue of lack of proper representation in the house would be another problem. The reason is that some minorities with their reliable candidates would be eliminated. The question now is how the interests of the candidate between the political parties and the electors **can** be handled. The idea of projecting the freedom of a voter to choose a candidate or representative in any of the country can be obtainable in Western world but in Africa it remains a problem due clannish interests and sometimes a constituency may be underdeveloped and the people would like to vote in a candidate from such constituency to reduce underdevelopment. The elimination method through lots is purely achieved on faith rather than reasoning. As a philosopher, is that the best method to apply? How can that be justified as the true and realistic method to avert irregularities and to have better representatives? Therefore, does Mill's idea of equal democracy radiate the objective interest and tenable too? The problem of democracy does not lie in its equality and liberty but in human nature, based on its wrong representation framework of some countries in the world, **which** is alien to their cultures. Based on the above idea, C.S. Momoh observed that elections and political parties are alien to our culture. But that is not a sufficient reason for anybody to advocate that they should not be adopted. As is

often the case with us, part of the problem is that we adopted many of these alien cultures without any effort to adjust them to our needs and circumstances.... there can be meaningful and responsible representation without political parties²². Although he was **interested in** the elections in Nigeria but objectively our emphasis should centre on two major areas: human nature, culture, and **the** democratic system of government. For us to have **a** meaningful and functional democratic system of government, there is a need to address the human nature–culture for possible adaptation. Therefore, the democratic system of government would be meaningful when the common goal of the nation/people is not undermined.

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